

Study of Adnexal Mass in Females in Central Part of Madhya Pradesh**Sushil Kumar Sharma¹, Prince Lokwani², Aditya Tignath³**^{1,2,3}Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Peoples college of Medical Sciences and research Centre Bhanpur, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh-462037

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Aditya Tignath

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Adnexal mass is a common clinical presentation among females of all age groups, but predominantly in reproduction age. It may be gynecological, non-gynecological, benign, or malignant. A clinical-pathological study can diagnose these adnexal masses.**Method:** 190 females aged between 14 years to 60 years were studied. The types of adnexal pathology were ovarian: 38 (20%) non-neoplasm, 97 (57%) benign and 37 (19.4%) malignant. In fallopian 12 (6.3%) ectopic pregnancy, 3 (1.5%) Hydrosalpinx-Blood ligament had 3 (1.57%) fibroids (true). Histopathologically malignant adnexal was found in 38 cases. Clinical findings versus histopathological findings were correlated.**Conclusion:** The present study of adnexal mass in reproductive females and the correlation between histopathological ultrasonographic and clinical diagnosis will help the obstetrician and gynecologist treat such patients efficiently to avoid morbidity and mortality.**Keywords:** Adnexal Mass, Histopathological, Ultra-Sonographical, Neoplasm, Malignant, Benign.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Adnexal tumors include a large spectrum of clinical presentation among women of all ages and are extremely common among reproductive age groups [1]. The term adnexia is derived from the pleural form of the Latin word adnexus, which means "appendage." The fallopian tube and ovary and their mesenteries are so closely related anatomically that they are often collectively called the adnexum [2].

The adolescent with adnexal masses are often diagnosed because they present with symptoms like abdominal pain, which is consistent with findings from other studies. Painless masses were found in 31%, 55–80% have palpable lesion masses on examination. Other complaints include distention in 8% to 24%, gastro-intestinal problems, 7 to 40%, urinary complaints in 3 to 18%, and endocrine abnormalities in 3 to 25%. Endo chronologically active masses may cause abnormal uterine bleeding, amenorrhea, or virilization.

The adnexal masses of gynecological origin include ovary, non-neoplastic masses of simple cyst, luteal cyst, hemorrhagic cyst, endometrial cyst, bulky ovaries like in PCOD [3]. Benign ovarian neoplasms are most common in mature cystic teratomas. Others are cystadenomas. Malignant ovarian neoplasm has dysgerminoma, granulosa cell tumors, and yolk sac tumors. Tubal hydrosalpinx, paratubal cyst, and tubo-ovarian abscess (pelvic inflammatory disease), and the uterine have muller-

ian anomalies, subserosal fibroids, which are very rare. Acute complications of adnexal masses include torsion and rupture of the cyst [4]. These complications need to be addressed on an emergency basis.

Hence, an attempt is made to evaluate various types of adnexal masses in females of reproductive age.

Material and Method

190 (one hundred ninety) females aged between 14 year to 60 years regularly visited the pathology department of the Peoples College of Medical Sciences and the research center hospital in Bhanpur, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh-462304 were studied.

Inclusion Criteria: The patients were diagnosed as adnexal and referred by the gynecology department. The patients who gave their consent in writing for the study were selected for the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Adnexal mass treated conservatory adnexal mass of non-gynecological origin. Pregnant women, immune-compromised women were excluded from the study.

Method: A detailed history of the menstrual cycle. Demographic factors, a complete general physical examination, and a gynecological examination were performed, and a provisional diagnosis was made. To evaluate the adnexal mass further, an ultrasonic examination consisting of trans-

abdominal and transvaginal sonography was carried out in suspicious cases of malignancy, where sonographic findings regarding the size of the adnexal mass, laterality, locularity, solid elements, hemorrhage, presence of ascites evidence of metastasis, and doppler studies with a pulsatility index (PI) and resistance index (RI) were assessed. An ultrasound diagnosis was made.

Laboratory tests consisting of a complete hemogram, blood sugar level, renal function tests, and other pre-operative investigations were done.

When malignancy was suspected clinically or ultrasonographically, advanced tests like CERT, MRI tumor markers, and ultra sound guided core biopsy

were done wherever feasible, and laparotomy was performed. Following surgery, specimens were sent for histo-pathological examinations, and reports were correlated with preoperative clinical and imaging findings. The accuracy of clinical and ultrasonic diagnoses was assessed.

The duration of the study was from January 2023 to June 2024.

Statistical analysis: Various types of adnexal pathological lesions or masses of different parts of female reproductive organs were classified with a percentage clinical diagnosis versus histopathological findings was also noted. The statistical analysis was carried out in SPSS software.

Figure 1: Mucinous cystadenoma

Figure 3: Serous cystadenocarcinoma

Figure 3: Mucinous cyst

Figure 4: Serous cystadenocarcinoma

Observation and Results

Table 1: Study of the relative frequency of adnexal mass

- Ovarian: 38 (20%) Non-Neoplastic, 97 (51%). Benign tumor, 37 (19.4%) malignant tumor, (Total = 72)
- Fallopian tube: 12 (6.3%) ectopic pregnancy, 3 (1.5%) hydrosalpinx (15=Total).
- Broad ligament: 3 (1.57%) Fibroid (true): (3 = Total)

Table 2: Study of Non-Neoplastic Simple Cyst, 9 (23.6%) Corpus tuteal Cyst, 22 (57.8%), Endometrioma, 2 (5.26%) ovarian ectopic frequency

Table 3: Histopathology Study of Benign Tumors

- Epithelial tumors: 40 (41.2%) serous cyst adenoma, 1 (1.03%) papillary serous cyst, 23 (23.7%) mucinous adenoma
- Germ Cell Tumor: 32 (32.9%) mature teratoma (dermatoid)
- Sex cord stromal tumor: 1 (1.03%) Fibroma

Table 4: Histopathological study of malignant tumors

- Epithelial tumors: 19 (51.3%) sebaceous cysts, 1 (2.70%) papillary serous cyst adenoma carcinomas, 6 (16.2%) mucinous cyst adenomas, and 2 (5.4%) endometrioid carcinomas.

- Germ cell tumor: 4 (10.8%) dysgerminoma, 2 (5.4%) immature teratoma, 1 (2.70%) embryonic cell carcinoma, and 2 (5.4%) metastatic carcinoma

Table 5: Study of clinical diagnosis versus histopathology in the diagnosis of malignant tumors: In histopathology, 30 are malignant, 19 absent of ma-

lignant. In clinical diagnosis, 8 cases were malignant and 133 had no malignant, 33 cases were malignant and 152 had no malignant.

Table 6: Study of USG diagnosis versus histopathology ultrasound diagnosis had 34 malignant and 4 had no malignant cyst. In histopathology, 15 had malignancy and 137 had no malignancy.

Table 1: Study of relative frequency of adnexal mass (Total No. of patients: 190)

Type of adnexal pathology	Number of patients	Percentage (%)
A. Ovarian		
Non-Neoplasm	38	20
Benign tumour	97	51
Total	172	19.4
B. Fallopian Tube		
Ectopic pregnancy	12	6.3
Hydro salpinx	3	1.5
Total	15	7.89
C. Broad ligament		
Fibroid (true)	3	1.57
Total	3	1.57
Grand Total	190	100

Figure 5: Study of relative frequency of adnexal mass

Table 2: Study of Non-Neoplastic ovarian Mass (Total No. of patients: 38)

Pathology	Number of patients (38)	Percentage (%)
Carpus cyst	5	13.1
Endometrioma	22	57.8
Ovarian ectopic	2	5.26

Figure 6: Study of Non-Neoplastic ovarian Mass

Table 3: Histo pathological study of benign tumors (Total No. of patients: 97)

Details	No. of patients	Percentage (%)
A. Epithelial tumour		
Serous cyst adenoma	40	41.2
Papillary serous cyst	1	1.03
Mucinous cyst adenoma	23	23.7
B. Germ cell Tumour		
Mature teratoma (dermoid)	32	32.9
C. Sex cord stromal tumour		
Fibroma	1	1.03
Total	97	100

Figure 7: Histo pathological study of benign tumors

Table 4: Histo pathological study of malignant tumor (Total No. of patients: 37)

Details	No of patients	Percentage (%)
A. Epithelial tumour		
Sebaceous cyst	19	51.3
Adeno carcinoma		
Papillary serous cyst adeno carcinoma	1	2.70
Mucinous cyst	6	16.2
Endometroid carcinoma	2	5.4
B. Germ cell tumour		
Dysgerminoma	4	10.8
Immature teratoma	2	5.4
Embryonal cell carcinoma	1	2.70
Metastatic carcinoma	2	5.4
Total	37	100

Figure 8: Histo pathological study of malignant tumor

Table 5: Comparative study of clinical diagnosis versus histo pathology in diagnosis of malignant tumors

Clinical diagnosis	Histo-pathology diagnosis		Total
	Malignancy present	Malignancy Absent	
Malignancy present	30	19	49
Malignancy Absent	8	133	141
Total	38	152	190

Figure 9: Comparative study of clinical diagnosis versus histo pathology in diagnosis of malignant tumors

Table 6: Comparative study of ultra sound diagnosis versus histopathology in diagnosis of malignant tumor

Ultra sound diagnosis	Histopathology diagnosis		Total
	Malignancy present	Malignancy Absent	
Malignancy present	34	15	49
Malignancy Absent	4	137	141
Total	38	152	190

Discussion

Present study of adnexal mass in females in the central part of Madhya Pradesh. Types of adnexal pathology included ovarian 38 (20%) non-neoplasm, 97 (51%) benign tumor, 37 (19.4%) malignant tumor, fallopian tube had 12 (6.3%) ectopic pregnancy, 3 (1.5%) had hydrosalpinx; broad ligament had 3 (1.7%) fibroid (true), (Table 1). In the comparison of clinical diagnosis versus histopathology, 38 cases had malignancy (Table 5), but during the comparison of ultrasound diagnosis versus histopathology, 34 malignancies were noted (Table 6) (Figure 1, 2, 3 and 4). These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7].

Majority of adnexal mass may regress on conservative treatment, but, some may require surgical intervention. A higher percentage of malignant ovarian tumors were observed in post-menopausal women, i.e., serous cyst adenocarcinoma [8]. Management of adnexal mass in adolescent girls is challenging. Most of these masses are non-neoplastic, but since many neoplastic masses like diamonds

occur in adolescent girls, In gynecological practice, effort is directed towards conservation of fertility and saving ovaries as much as possible, but saving ovaries depends on the pathology of the adnexal mass [9]. Irregular menses and lower abdominal pain are associated with the adnexal mass of reproductive organs.

It is also reported that simple cysts are observed in the reproductive age of females. It is due to a hormonal imbalance caused by an immature hypothalamo hypophyseal axis [10].

Tumor markers were done for all suspected neoplastic masses since CA-125 had high sensitivity and less specificity; therefore, other tumor markers like AFP, CA19-9, and LDH were also done. It is also noted that CA-125 values were high in tubero-ovarian mass due to tuberculosis. Moreover, serum CA-125 can be elevated in various other conditions, like endometriosis, pelvic inflammatory disease, tuberculosis, peritonitis, pancreas, or colorectal cancer [11].

Summary and Conclusion

Present study of adnexal mass in females in the central part of Madhya Pradesh. Adnexal masses in reproductive age were mostly non-neoplastic and benign, whereas those in the peri- and postmenopausal age groups were malignant. The majority of adnexal masses were of ovarian origin. The correlative and comparison study of clinical, ultrasonographic, and histopathological adnexal mass had accuracy in its diagnostic value, but the present study demands further genetic, nutritional, hormonal, and pathophysiological studies. The exact cause, process, and formation of adnexal mass are still unclear.

Limitation of Study: Owing to the tertiary location of the research center, the small number of patients, and the lack of the latest techniques, we have limited findings and results. This research work was approved by the ethical committee of the Peoples College of Medical Sciences and Research Center in Bhanpur, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh-462038.

References

1. A bell MR, Holtz F: Ovarian Neoplasms in Childhood and Adolescence II. Tumors of non-germ cell origin Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol. 1965, 93, 850–53.
2. Ash AK, Badaway A: Laparoscopy and spread of ovarian cancer Lancet 1995, 346; 709–711.
3. Jeffcoate S: Principles of Gynecology, 8th edition, 2014, 490–527.
4. Rahul Hain JA: Adnexal mass in the postmenopausal patient clin. Obstet. Gynecol. 2015, 58 (1); 53–65.
5. Sharma I, Sharma U, Detta UC: Pathology of an Ovarian Tumor A hospital-based study, Int. J. Med. Sc. Clin. Inv. 2014, 1(6); 284-6.
6. Radhamani S, Akhita MV: Evaluation of adnexal masses and correlation of clinical sonological and histopathological findings in adnexal masses Inter J. Scientific Study 2017, 4 (11); 88–92.
7. Balbi GC, Musone R: Women with a pelvic mass indication of malignancy European J. Gynecoloncol. 2001, 22 (6); 459–62.
8. Padilla LA, Radosevich DM: Accuracy of the pelvic examination in detecting adnexal masses, Obstet Gynecol. 2000, 96; 593–8.
9. Drake J: Diagnosis and management of the adnexal mass, Am. Fam. Phys. 1998, 57 (10); 2471–73.
10. Curtin JP: Management of adnexal mass Gynecol. Ancol: 1991, 55 (3); 42–6.
11. Mani Vasakan J: A study of benign adnexal masses Int. J. Reprod. Contracept. Obstet. Gynecol. 2012, 1; 12–16.